

Neural Operator and Transformer Architectures for Thermo-Mechanical Strain Prediction in Electronic Packaging

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Abstract—High-fidelity thermo-mechanical Finite-element method (FEM) simulations are required to predict strain evolution and reliability behavior in advanced electronic components. The high computational cost of these simulations limits large-scale parametric exploration, especially in the case of nonlinear plasticity, multi-material interfaces, and complex thermal cycling. Recent advances in scientific machine learning have introduced transformer-based neural operators capable of learning partial differential equations (PDE) solution mappings on general geometries, yet their applicability to nonlinear solid mechanics problems in power electronic modules remains largely unexplored.

In this work, we investigate the accuracy of predictions of a transformer-based network in learning element-wise elastic and plastic strain fields for thermo-mechanical simulations of electronic assemblies. Two architectures are studied: (i) a geometry and physics-aware neural operator incorporating structured token interactions, and (ii) a data-driven global operator, based on unrestricted self-attention, that learns nonlinear thermo-mechanical solution operators directly from unstructured finite-element representations. These models are trained on coupled transient simulations under varying heat generation rates, heating durations, and geometric perturbations, including structural modifications within the sinter layer.

The problem formulation includes strain prediction for unstructured finite-element meshes using material descriptors, geometric features, spatial coordinates, and global thermal loading parameters as input. A comparative study is performed to assess the predictive accuracy, scalability, and computational efficiency for nonlinear elastic-plastic response prediction. The results are encouraging, and it proves that transformer-based models accurately reproduce strain predictions across diverse loading conditions while providing substantial acceleration over conventional FEM simulations. The study highlights the comparison between physics-aware token aggregation and full self-attention in balancing accuracy, computational complexity, and other factors.

This work provides an efficient framework for predicting

thermo-mechanical responses in multi-material electronic systems, enabling accelerated reliability assessment and efficient design-space exploration.

Index Terms—Thermo-Mechanical Simulation, Power Electronic Module, Neural Operator, Transformer Architecture, Unstructured Finite-Element Mesh, Surrogate Modeling.

I. INTRODUCTION

Modern electronic assemblies and packaging used in high-performance applications are subjected to complex thermo-mechanical stresses arising from concentrated heat generation, multi-material components, and transient operating cycles. These thermal stresses, coupled with nonlinear material behavior, generate strain fields that govern fatigue, defect propagation, and long-term reliability.

These assemblies typically consist of multiple material interfaces, including silicon, copper, solder, ceramics, and sintered die-attach layers, which exhibit temperature-dependent material properties and nonlinear hardening. Transient thermal loading induces thermo-mechanical stress distributions and localized strain concentrations, particularly near interfaces and geometric discontinuities.

Finite-element simulations for such highly nonlinear coupled problems are computationally expensive [1]–[4]. For meshes containing on the order of 10^5 elements, a single simulation for one loading case may require several hours of computation. This cost severely limits large-scale reliability screening after production and prevents real-time health monitoring during field operation. Therefore, there is a need for the development of accurate and computationally efficient surrogate models [5].

A further challenge arises from geometric variability and re-meshing. Even small structural modifications, such as introducing voids in the sinter layer, require complete regeneration of the unstructured mesh, leading to changes in element

count, topology, orientation, and aspect ratio across simulations. The developed surrogate models must therefore remain permutation-invariant to element ordering while being robust to evolving discretizations and nonlinear transient coupling.

In this work, we address these challenges by investigating the following transformer-based neural operator architectures that operate directly on unstructured finite-element representations [6]–[8].

- **Model A:** A geometry- and physics-aware neural operator incorporating structured token interactions and conditioning mechanisms.
- **Model B:** A data-driven global operator based on unrestricted self-attention that learns the nonlinear mapping directly from element-level representations.

The objective is to assess predictive accuracy and robustness under simultaneous variability in thermal loading, geometric perturbations, and mesh regeneration, thereby establishing the feasibility of attention-based neural operators as scalable surrogates for nonlinear thermo-mechanical simulations in electronic packaging.

II. THERMO-MECHANICAL MODELING AND DATASET GENERATION

A. Coupled Transient Thermo-Mechanical Simulation

The data generation pipeline includes sequentially coupled transient thermal and structural finite element simulations of a heterogeneous electronic assembly. The assembly comprises 34 individual geometric bodies and 11 distinct materials, including silicon, copper, solder, ceramic substrates, and sintered die-attach layers. This forms a multi-material stack that is representative of advanced power electronic packaging [1], [2], [4]. The results of the transient thermal analysis are the temperature distributions corresponding to the applied volumetric heat generation rate in the chip region. The thermal loading cycle consists of heating, holding, and cooling phases. The applied thermal loading induces spatially non-uniform temperature fields, which in turn generate stress distributions in the multi-material structure. The total simulation duration is 3000 s, discretized into 55 time steps. The defined material properties include temperature-dependent linear elasticity and nonlinear elastic-plastic constitutive modeling with combined isotropic and kinematic hardening. The resulting response evolves over the transient loading cycle, producing stress redistribution and localized strain concentrations within the assembly.

B. Loading and Geometric Variability

Thermal loading is parameterized by the volumetric heat generation rate, heating duration, cooling duration, and base temperature. We create a cylindrical hole in the sinter layer to introduce geometric variation. This hole is parameterized by its radius and spatial position. Sobol sampling is used to generate uniformly distributed samples of the thermal and geometric parameters. The following parameters are treated as variable inputs in the study:

Fig. 1. (Left) Electronic assembly model with some components hidden for visualization clarity. (Right) Modified configuration with a cylindrical hole introduced in the sinter layer.

- Volumetric heat generation rate
- Heating duration
- Hole radius
- Spatial position of the hole

Each geometric modification results in complete re-meshing of the domain. As a result, the unstructured meshes vary in:

- Element count
- Connectivity and topology
- Element orientation and aspect ratio
- Local refinement patterns

The generated meshes contain approximately 1.8×10^5 elements on average, with substantial variation across configurations. The need for re-meshing makes the learning problem fundamentally different from fixed-grid surrogate modeling. This introduces additional complexity in achieving discretization-invariant predictions.

C. Learning Formulation

For the problem formulation, we consider an unstructured finite element mesh containing N elements, where N varies across configurations due to geometric changes and subsequent re-meshing. Each element $i \in \{1, \dots, N\}$ is represented by a feature vector

$$\mathbf{x}_i \in \mathbb{R}^{10}, \quad (1)$$

encoding material identifiers and geometric descriptors, including aspect ratio, shape anisotropy, principal axes, and centroid coordinates.

The thermal loading parameters are the same for all the elements; hence, we consider them as global parameters represented by a conditioning vector

$$\mathbf{c} \in \mathbb{R}^3, \quad (2)$$

containing volumetric heat generation rate (HEAT), heating duration (TON), and the current time step.

For a given configuration, the element-wise feature matrix is

$$\mathbf{X} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 10}. \quad (3)$$

The learning objective is to approximate a nonlinear operator [5], [7]

$$\mathcal{F} : (\mathbf{X}, \mathbf{c}) \rightarrow \mathbf{Y}, \quad (4)$$

where

$$\mathbf{Y} \in \mathbb{R}^{N \times 2} \quad (5)$$

contains the equivalent elastic and plastic von Mises strains for all elements.

An important consideration is that the number of elements N varies across configurations due to re-meshing; hence, the learned operator must remain stable under changes in mesh topology and element ordering [9]–[12]. In addition, nonlinear material properties and transient thermal loading lead to strong global coupling across the assembly components. The model must therefore capture both local geometric effects and long-range thermo-mechanical interactions.

In the following section, two transformer-based architectures are detailed for approximating the operator \mathcal{F} : a structured physics-aware attention model (Model A) and a global self-attention baseline (Model B).

III. NEURAL OPERATOR ARCHITECTURES

In this section, we describe the transformer-based architectures that we have designed to approximate the nonlinear thermo-mechanical solution. Both models are trained and validated directly on unstructured finite-element meshes and predict element-wise equivalent elastic and plastic strain fields under varying thermal loading conditions and geometric configurations. Both architectures share the same learning formulation, but they differ fundamentally in how spatial interactions and global conditioning are incorporated.

A. Geometry- and Physics- Aware Operator Architecture (Model A)

Model A is developed as a structured neural operator tailored for large unstructured finite-element meshes. For the given element descriptors and global thermal conditions, the architecture learns a nonlinear mapping as follows:

$$\mathcal{F} : (\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^N, \mathbf{c}) \rightarrow \{\mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^N, \quad (6)$$

where \mathbf{y}_i denotes the equivalent elastic and plastic strain components at the element level.

The architecture of Model A introduces structured interaction mechanisms that incorporate physics-aligned inductive bias while preserving global information exchange [9], [11], [12]. It is formulated according to the following design principles:

Mesh-Consistent Element Representation: Element-wise geometric and material descriptors are encoded into a structured latent space that captures relevant physics of material heterogeneity and spatial configuration. Thus, the design promotes consistent operator behavior across variable-size meshes and enhances robustness under re-meshing, while remaining invariant to element ordering.

Global Thermal Conditioning: Thermal loading parameters are combined into a global conditioning vector that

modulates the operator response. This enables adaptive strain prediction across varying heat-generation rates and transient thermal loading.

Structured Long-Range Interaction Modeling: Model A employs structured interaction pathways that combine local and aggregated global information flow to capture long-range thermo-mechanical dependencies while maintaining near-linear computational scaling with respect to mesh size [5], [6], [13], [14].

Geometry-Aware Feature Integration: Spatial coordinates and geometric descriptors are fused in a manner that preserves relative geometric relationships. This enables the operator to resolve localized strain concentrations associated with material interfaces, structural anisotropy, and geometric variations.

Decoupled Strain Prediction: Dedicated regression mappings are used for elastic and plastic strain components, which helps improve stability when modeling nonlinear elastic-plastic behavior.

Computational Characteristics: Let N denote the number of mesh elements, D the latent dimension, and L the number of operator layers. The computational complexity scales as

$$\mathcal{O}(L(ND + D^2)), \quad (7)$$

which is approximately linear in N . This is one of the most important features of this architecture, as it significantly decreases the computational cost for large unstructured meshes typical of high-fidelity thermo-mechanical simulations.

Physical Interpretation: Model A approximates a nonlinear thermo-mechanical operator of the form

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \mathcal{F}(G, M, T) \quad (8)$$

where G represents geometric descriptors, M denotes material properties, and T corresponds to thermal loading parameters. The operator \mathcal{F} is a learned nonlinear mapping that approximates the coupled thermo-mechanical response at the element level.

B. Data-Driven Global Operator (Model B)

Model B functions as a high-capacity, fully data-driven baseline architecture. The learning objective remains identical to Model A: given element descriptors and global thermal conditions, the model learns a nonlinear mapping

$$\mathcal{G} : (\{\mathbf{x}_i\}_{i=1}^N, \mathbf{c}) \rightarrow \{\mathbf{y}_i\}_{i=1}^N, \quad (9)$$

where \mathbf{y}_i represents the equivalent elastic and plastic strain components at the element level.

Unlike the design of Model A, Model B considers all mesh elements as components of a unified latent system and learns strain behavior using unrestricted global self-attention [7], [15]. This architecture does not impose any explicit physics-aligned inductive bias and instead depends solely on dense cross-element feature interactions.

The modeling strategy is described as follows:

Global Representation of Mesh Elements: The computational domain is defined at the element level, enabling the

model to learn strain responses directly from local descriptors and ensuring robustness to variations in mesh topology, discretization, and geometric complexity.

Spatially Aware Feature Encoding: Spatial information is integrated through enriched coordinate representations that preserve both local and global geometric features [16]. These representations enable the identification of spatially varying deformation patterns and localized strain concentrations that develop under thermo-mechanical loading conditions.

Integration of Global Loading Conditions: Since strain evolution is significantly influenced by the assembly’s thermal operating conditions, global loading parameters are incorporated into the model formulation. This enables the prediction of localized deformation behavior while preserving consistency with the overall thermo-mechanical state of the system.

Dense Global Interaction Modeling: Interactions among mesh elements are learned through unrestricted global information exchange facilitated by the self-attention mechanism [15]. This approach enables the model to capture long-range thermo-mechanical dependencies resulting from material interfaces, geometric discontinuities, and nonlocal deformation effects without imposing predefined interaction pathways.

Computational Characteristics: Model B employs dense global interactions among mesh elements, enabling information exchange throughout the entire computational domain. Although this approach offers substantial representational capacity for modeling complex thermo-mechanical behavior, the associated computational and memory costs increase rapidly with mesh size. Consequently, Model B serves as a representative global-attention baseline for comparison with more structured operator-learning methods.

Physical Interpretation: Model B approximates a nonlinear mapping of the form

$$\varepsilon_{eq} = \mathcal{G}(G, M, T) \quad (10)$$

where G represents geometric descriptors, M denotes material properties, and T corresponds to thermal loading parameters. The operator \mathcal{G} is a learned nonlinear mapping in which geometry, material response, and thermal loading are coupled through global self-attention mechanisms. Consequently, Model B serves as a highly expressive data-driven baseline for evaluating the benefits of introducing structured interaction mechanisms in Model A.

IV. RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

The models were trained on 9,625 samples and validated on 2,365 samples. Both sets were mutually exclusive, i.e., the heat-generation values used for validation were not present during training. For training, 175 distinct heat-generation values were considered, each evaluated over 55 time steps, resulting in $175 \times 55 = 9,625$ samples. Similarly, 43 distinct heat-generation values were used for validation, leading to $43 \times 55 = 2,365$ samples. Each configuration corresponds to a variable mesh and time step and contains approximately 1.8×10^5 elements on average. The evaluation results presented

here are for different material properties, transient thermal loading, and mesh variability. In this section, actual-scale accuracy refers to the prediction accuracy computed by comparing the predicted and reference FEM strain values in their original physical units, after reversing any normalization applied during training.

A. Model A: Geometry- and Physics-Aware Neural Operator

1) *Overall Accuracy:* Model A achieves an overall actual-scale accuracy of 96.20% on the training set and 93.62% on the validation set. The evaluated mean R^2 values are 0.9977 for training and 0.9933 for validation. These results indicate strong predictive generalization for unseen geometries and thermal loading conditions.

2) *Elastic and Plastic Components:* For the validation set, the accuracy for elastic strain reaches 94.25%, whereas for plastic strain, the accuracy is 93.00%. The slightly higher error in the plastic component is consistent with its stronger nonlinearity and path-dependent behavior.

3) *Accuracy Distribution:* The analysis of the validation set shows that only 0.47% of the validation samples fall below 80% accuracy, and 8.41% have an accuracy below 90%. Most of the calculated accuracies lie in the mid-90% range (see Fig. 2 and Fig. 3).

Fig. 2. Training actual-scale accuracy for Model A: elastic component (left) and plastic component (right).

Fig. 3. Validation actual-scale accuracy for Model A: elastic component (left) and plastic component (right).

The distribution of mean actual-scale accuracy is shown in Fig. 4. These results demonstrate strong predictive robustness, given the fact that each geometric variation results in complete re-meshing of the assembly.

4) *Prediction Consistency and Generalization:* Parity plots exhibit tight clustering around the identity line for both elastic and plastic components, consistent with validation $R^2 > 0.99$ (Fig. 5). The aggregated values over heat bins show that the validation accuracy remains consistently above 90% (Fig. 6), confirming stable predictive behavior across the full spectrum.

Fig. 4. Histogram of mean actual-scale accuracy for Model A, showing the percentage of training and validation samples within each accuracy bin.

Fig. 5. Parity plots for Model A showing predicted versus actual strain values: elastic component (left) and plastic component (right) for training and validation samples.

Fig. 6. Mean actual-scale accuracy across heat-value bins for Model A, comparing training and validation performance.

Overall, Model A demonstrates strong predictive accuracy and stability under nonlinear transient thermo-mechanical conditions and large unstructured mesh variability.

B. Model B: Data-Driven Global Operator

1) *Overall Accuracy:* Model B achieves an overall actual-scale training accuracy of 93.23% and a validation accuracy of 92.15%, with mean R^2 values of 0.9924 on the training set and 0.9893 on the validation set. These results indicate that global self-attention effectively captures the dominant features of the strain field, even with large mesh sizes and strongly nonlinear material behavior.

2) *Elastic and Plastic Components:* For the validation set, elastic strain accuracy reaches 91.29%, while plastic strain accuracy reaches 93.02%. The larger dispersion in the elastic component suggests increased sensitivity to discretization variability compared to Model A (see Fig. 7 and Fig. 8).

Fig. 7. Training actual-scale accuracy for Model B: elastic component (left) and plastic component (right).

Fig. 8. Validation actual-scale accuracy for Model B: elastic component (left) and plastic component (right).

Fig. 9. Histogram of mean actual-scale accuracy for Model B, showing the percentage of training and validation samples within each accuracy bin.

3) *Accuracy Distribution:* Within the validation set, only 0.93% of the configurations exhibit accuracies below 80%, while 15.48% fall below 90%. Although most configurations maintain high accuracy, the distribution is broader than that of Model A (Fig. 9). This result suggests that the global-attention formulation preserves strong predictive capability but demonstrates slightly increased sensitivity to mesh regeneration and geometric variability.

4) *Prediction Consistency and Generalization:* For this model, parity plots demonstrate strong linear alignment between predicted and actual strain values, reflected in a validation R^2 of 0.9893 (Fig. 10). Although prediction dispersion is moderately higher than that observed for Model A, particularly for the elastic component, the model continues to provide physically meaningful strain predictions across geometrically diverse unstructured meshes. The consistent accuracy observed throughout the thermal loading spectrum further indicates robust generalization beyond the conditions represented in the training dataset (Fig. 11).

Model B presents strong predictive performance for nonlinear elastic-plastic behavior on large unstructured meshes, though with slightly higher dispersion under geometric variability than Model A.

Fig. 10. Parity plots for Model B showing predicted versus actual strain values: elastic component (left) and plastic component (right) for training and validation samples.

Fig. 11. Mean actual-scale accuracy across heat-value bins for Model B, comparing training and validation performance.

V. CONCLUSION

This work addresses the challenge of predicting elastic and plastic strain fields for electronic assemblies with varying thermal loading and geometric perturbations. The problem was formulated as a neural operator learning task defined over large unstructured finite-element meshes containing approximately 1.8×10^5 elements on average.

The following challenges were taken into account in this study:

- Strongly nonlinear elastic-plastic material response
- Varying volumetric heat generation rates and heating durations
- Transient thermo-mechanical loading
- Large geometric perturbations
- Significant variation in mesh topology, element size, aspect ratio, and orientation

The trained models were thus required to demonstrate strong predictive capability of the strain fields, given the changing loading parameters and continuously evolving discretizations and geometric configurations. Model A achieved 96.20% (training) and 93.62% (validation) overall actual-scale accuracy with mean R^2 exceeding 0.99, while Model B achieved 93.23% (training) and 92.15% (validation) with validation $R^2 = 0.9893$. Parity plots show close alignment with the identity line, consistent with validation R^2 values above 0.99 for Model A and 0.9893 for Model B. The aggregated accuracy over the heat-value bins remains consistently over 90% for Model A and 88% for Model B. We have achieved our objective of computational acceleration compared to the FEM

simulations. A single coupled thermo-mechanical FEM simulation, including all 55 time steps, requires approximately 8-12 hours. In contrast, the trained Model A required approximately 18.2 seconds to predict the strain values for 190,095 elements on an NVIDIA RTX A5000 GPU. Thus, we conclude that the attention-based neural operator architectures serve as an effective modeling approach for large-scale nonlinear thermo-mechanical simulations in electronic packaging. The proposed frameworks also remain robust to both loading variability and geometric mesh regeneration, enabling accelerated parametric exploration. The predicted strain fields can be directly utilized for damage-factor computation and fatigue-life estimation, and can be deployed in cloud-based infrastructures to support real-time reliability assessments for electronic assemblies.

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